

**Synthesis and De-emulsifying Activity of some
Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid Esters**

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UNSATURATED ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) hydroxyesters have shown good de-emulsifying activity for petroleum emulsions¹. In this paper the preparation of some of the EDTA esters and their de-emulsifying activity are reported. *N,N,N',N'*-Tetrakis(cyclohexyl acetate)ethylenediamine has been prepared by refluxing H₂SO₄ salt of EDTA and cyclohexanol in xylene, *N,N,N',N'*-Tetrakis(1-octyl acetate)ethylenediamine and *N,N,N',N'*-tetrakis(1-cetyl acetate)ethylenediamine have

also been synthesised by treating EDTA with 1-octyl and 1-cetyl alcohols in the presence of thionyl chloride. Higher yields have been obtained than that reported in the literature² and at the same time the reaction time has been drastically reduced. All EDTA esters show sharp carbonyl stretching peak at 1 747–1 742 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra.

Experimental

Ir spectra (near) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 177 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian CFT-20 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard.

N,N,N',N'-Tetrakis(cyclohexyl acetate)ethylenediamine: A mixture of H₂SO₄ salt of EDTA³ (0.01 mol) and cyclohexanol (20 ml) in xylene (30 ml) was refluxed for 12 h using a Dean-Stark apparatus. The reaction mixture was then cooled, and xylene and excess cyclohexanol were removed under reduced pressure. The residue was diluted with water (30 ml), basified with K₂CO₃ and extracted with chloroform. The extract, on evaporation of solvent, gave a bright red coloured viscous liquid which was purified by passing through silica gel column using chloroform as eluent, (3.2 g, 51.6%); $\nu_{\max}(\text{neat})$ 2 942 (aliphatic CH), 1 747s (C–CO), 1 190 (C–(CO)–O), 1 118 (O–C–C) and 1 430 cm⁻¹ (CH₂ of cyclohexyl); $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 1.2–2.0 (40H, m), 3.0 (4H, t, N–CH₂–CH₂–N), 3.7 (8H, s, 4×N–CH₂CO) and 4.9 (4H, m, 4×O–CH); *m/z* M⁺ 620(3), 493(6), 420(6), 419(16), 340(7) and 310(100).

N,N,N',N'-Tetrakis(1-octyl acetate)ethylenediamine: A mixture of EDTA (3 g, 0.01 mol) and thionyl chloride (5 ml) was stirred for 8 h and left overnight. 1-Octanol (5.2 g, 0.04 mol) was then added to the mixture over a period of one hour while stirring at room temperature when HCl and SO₂ gases were evolved. Stirring was continued for 30 h at room temperature and the mixture was diluted with water (30 ml). It was basified with K₂CO₃, extracted with chloroform, washed with water and dried. The solvent was then evaporated and the crude material purified through column chromatography over silica gel using hexane-benzene (1:1) as eluent to get a yellow liquid (2.6 g, 35%); $\nu_{\max}(\text{neat})$ 2 980 and 2 840 (aliphatic CH), 1 742 (–C–CO–), 1 200 (–C(CO)–O) and 1 111 cm⁻¹ (–O–C–C–); $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 0.85–1.7 (60H, m), 2.35 (4H, t, N–CH₂CH₂–N), 3.55 (8H, s, 4×N–CH₂–CO) and 3.6 (8H, t, 4×O–CH₂).

N,N,N',N'-Tetrakis(1-cetyl acetate)ethylenediamine: Similar procedure was used as above for the preparation except that the temperature was maintained at 50–60°, (4 g, 33%); $\nu_{\max}(\text{neat})$ 2 917 and 2 846 (aliphatic CH), 1 745 (C–CO–), 1 206 (C–(CO)–O) and 1 106 cm⁻¹ (–O–C–C); $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 0.85–1.7 (124H, m), 2.3 (4H, t, N–CH₂–CH₂–N), 3.55 (8H, 4×N–CH₂–CO) and 3.6 (8H, t, 4×O–CH₂).

Results and Discussion

The esters were tested as de-emulsifying agents in a synthetic emulsion of Balol crude oil. A mixture of Balol crude (80 ml) and water (20 ml) was mixed in Hamilton Beach for 7 min to make a stable emulsion. The EDTA esters were added to the emulsion to test their effectiveness as de-emulsifying agents in different concentrations. The emulsion was heated for 2–3 h at 80–85°.

The results (Table 1) reveal that the addition of *N,N,N',N'*-tetrakis(cyclohexyl acetate)ethylenediamine resulted in separation of 50% of water from the emulsion at 1500–2000 ppm level within 2 h. While increasing the concentration of EDTA tetracyclohexyl ester beyond 2000 ppm, the separation of water decreased.

TABLE 1—DE-EMULSIFYING ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUND

Sl. no.	Name of de-emulsifier	Conc. of de-emulsifier (mg/100 ml)	Time (h)	Sep of water (ml)
<i>N,N,N',N'</i> -Tetrakis(cyclohexyl acetate)ethylenediamine				
1.		100	3	6
2.		150	2	10
3.		200	2	10
4.		300	3	8
5.		400	3	6
<i>N,N,N',N'</i> -Tetrakis(1-octyl acetate)ethylenediamine				
6.		100	4	—
7.		200	3	2
8.		300	3	2
9.		400	3	3
10.		500	3	5 ^a
<i>N,N,N',N'</i> -Tetrakis(1-cetyl acetate)ethylenediamine				
11.		100	2	6
12.		200	2	10
13.		300	2	8
14.		400	2	6
15.		500	2	5

* Emulsion of Balol crude oil was heated at 80 85°.
^a Turbid.

In the case of *N,N,N',N'*-tetrakis(1-octyl acetate)ethylenediamine, the separation of water from crude oil emulsion is not very encouraging. Even when the ester is added at 5000 ppm level the separation of water from emulsion is only about 25% or so; at the same time the separated water presents turbid appearance indicating the tendency for the formation of invert emulsion. On the other hand, *N,N,N',N'*-tetrakis(1-cetyl acetate)ethylenediamine gave 50% water separation even at 2000 ppm. To confirm the effectiveness of these esters as de-emulsifying agents a blank reading was taken by heating the emulsion at 80–85° for 4 h which did not result in any separation of water.

By observing the de-emulsifying effect of these esters it is possible to conclude that the de-emulsify-

NOTES

ing activity is more in the case of *N,N,N',N'*-tetrakis-(cyclohexyl acetate)ethylenediamine.

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